

Restricted Woman in Girish Karnad's Naga-Mandala

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Abstract

Girish Karnad has emerged as a living legend in contemporary Indian English Drama. The male dominance is apparent in all the plays of Girish Karnad. In his plays the women characters became pawns in the games that the male characters play and are relegated to background. In 'Nagamandala' he not only exposes male chauvinism, the oppression of women, the great injustice done to them by men and patriarchal culture but also stealthily deflates the story of Rani. In the Indian tradition, the woman is forced to love her husband even though he is not to be her aspiration. Appanna visits Rani only in noon to have his lunch. The picture of Rani, shut in old and huge house for most part of the day and night, alone. He warns her not to talk to anyone other than him in a server indictment of male-dominated Hindu society. Appanna suspects his wife of adultery asks her to take snake ordeal to prove her chastity. Rani's trial reminds us of Sita in The Ramayana and it shows the affinities with traditional Indian values.

Keywords: Male chauvinism, oppression, patriarchy, adultery, snake ordeal and chastity.

Girish Karnad is regarded as one of the three great writers of the contemporary Indian drama, the other two being Vijay Tendulkar and Badal Sircar. While Badal Sircar and Vijay Tendulkar deal with the problems of the middle class, Girish Karnad takes refuge in the Indian myths and legends and makes them a vehicle of a new vision. Karnad says that the issues of the present world find their parallels in the myths and fable of the past, giving new meanings and insights reinforcing the theme. By transcending the limits of time and space, myth provides flashes of insights into life and its mystery. They form an internal part of cultural consciousness of the land, with different meanings and it reflects the contemporary issues.

Girish Karnad presents Rani as the only child of her parents and she is their queen. When Rani grew up, her parents get her married to Appanna whose parents are no more. When she enters the house of Appanna he asks his wife to stay inside, shuts the door and locks it from outside and leaves the place. Such a danger treatment breaks her into pieces and in the absence of love and care, under the stress of loneliness and isolation she dreams like a child, longing for parents and their affection. She imagines that she is carried away by an eagle.

She dreams like child and she feels that the eagle is rescuer from the difficult condition in her life. The dream makes her to forget the torture that her husband gives her.

Appanna leaves his wife alone and he spends his night with a concubine. Kurudava a friend of his mother gives some roots to Rani to feed Appanna and make as love maker. She tries to give the root through food to Appanna but she fears if there would be a negative result of that on her husband. Therefore she puts the liquid of root into the anthill. Rani is a traditional Indian woman who does not dare to do any harmful act against husband. When she pours the curry into the anthill there lives a cobra called Naga which tastes the liquid and starts to love her. Naga took the shape of Appanna and showers love on Rani. But Appanna had the usual behavior during day time. Rani also experiences the dichotomy of the warm loving embrace of her ideal lover and the cold, authoritative contemptuous behavior of her real husband Appanna. She is in a dilemma but accepts the difference between the passionate lover and the dominating husband because she has inherited the submissiveness by tradition. The husband's dominating nature is finally expressed in Rani's words "but day or night, one motto does not change; don't ask questions. Do as I tell you"(51). When he comes to know that Rani is pregnant he beats her with at most anger. Because he only knows that he has not touched her. He takes her to the villagers and asks her to prove her chastity.

The concept of chastity is trusted only on women and not on men. The village elders know well that Appanna has a concubine and lives with her and not with his wife. They never take that as a destruction of moral code and never question him why he is doing such a degraded activity. But when Appanna questions about Rani's chastity, the village elders come readily to test Rani's fidelity through barbaric ordeals like holding the red hot-iron in the hand, plunging the hand into the boiling oil and the ant-hill.

Appanna has an illegal relationship with another women but he does not accept his wife having extra marital relationship. Appanna did not even pay heed to Rani's words:

Why are you humiliating me like this? Why are you stripping me naked in front of the whole village? Why don't you kill instead? I would have killed myself. But there is not even rope in this house for me to use (p.33).

The words of Rani present her very sad condition in her marital life. Rani has the personality as a traditional Indian wife who believes her husband as a god in her life. Rani slaps herself on her cheeks when she believes that she is going to do something against her husband. It is clear that Rani has much social pressure so she behaves according to the norms of male-dominated society. Through the image of Rani, Girish Karnad presents evils related to female in patriarchal society. Traditional institution of marriage is not good for women in Indian society. Because such tradition women have secondary place and they are not treated as equal to men in marital life.

Girish Karnad presents the problem of chastity which is majorly related with women. As Sita has to face fire ordeal to prove her chastity in the presence of all elders and her husband, Girish Karnad presents snake ordeal for Rani to prove her chastity. It shows even the Goddess Sita was exploited in the name of chastity. The concept ordeal is related with only women from the ancient age to modern age. Such incidents show the reality that women in Indian society have only the secondary place and they have to suffer in the name of purity in marital life.

Appanna enjoys extra-marital relationship but Rani has to face snake ordeal to prove her chastity in the society. Karnad presents the problem of social attitude which makes injustice to women. At the end, to prove her chastity Rani accepts the snake ordeal and she puts hands into the snake pit. When she pulls the snake, it binds itself around her and does not bite. She is declared as a goddess. Appanna felt guilty and lives with her. The submissive woman has started to understand her equal rights in family and society. The suppressed woman reacts against the orthodox male-dominated society:

I was a stupid, ignorant girl when you brought me here. But now I am a woman, a wife, and I am going to be a mother. I am not a parrot. Not a cat or a sparrow. Why don't you take it on trust that I have a mind and explain this charade to me? Why do you play these games? Why do you change like a chameleon from day to night?(p.32)

These words of Rani present herself as conscious woman who justifies her equal rights in the family.

Nagamandala portrays the commoditization of woman in a society where woman are not valued as objects of individuality but as objects of possession. They are subjected to social indoctrination and their voices are marginalized. The place of woman is shaped by topical references and the idea of a woman holding power of any sort over a man attacks the male ego.

The submissive Rani has emerged into a confident Rani towards the end of the play, when Appanna objects her going and talking to Kurudava she snarls at Appanna, "if you don't let her go, I'll... (shocked at her anger, Appanna lets her go)"(57). After the snake ordeal Rani becomes the head of the family. Appanna accepts her superiority and says to her that she is not a common person and she is a goddess. However Rani, unlike Appanna never orders him. Thus showing a trace of matriarchy at the end, the play anticipates that matriarchy is to follow patriarchy if our society is to change for better.

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